

An Attempt to Account for the Properties of the Strong Electrolytes in Solution by Applying the Principles of Quantum Theory

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It has been pointed out that the expression for κ (kappa) in the Debye-Hückel theory of the strong electrolytes require modification. A modified expression for κ has been derived which appears to fit the experimental data well. The formation of ion-pairs in dilute solutions of 1 : 1 electrolytes has been discussed. Equations for the potential energy, kinetic energy and total energy of the ion-pairs have been derived. It has been pointed out that they do not vary with dilution so long as the effective ionic diameter remains constant. In dilute solutions the ion-pairs do not influence one another.

Attempt has been made to apply the principles of quantum theory to the rotatory motion of the ion-pairs in solution.

In previous publications¹⁻⁴ it has been shown that the Debye-Hückel expression for kappa in the theory of the strong electrolytes requires modification. The modified expression for kappa (κ_m) may be written for the 1 : 1 electrolytes as

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{4\pi e^2 \Sigma n (f_o/f)}{DkT} \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where, e represents the electronic charge, $\Sigma n = 2n$ the sum of the positive and negative ions per cm^3 , D the dielectric constant, k the Boltzmann constant, T the absolute temperature and f_o/f the ratio of the mean activity coefficients of the ions, outside and inside, respectively, of the ion atmosphere surrounding the central positively charged ion.

If the ions behave as neutral particles the distance L between them should be as

$$(1/2n)^{1/3} = L = 2\pi a x \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or } L/x = 2\pi a \quad (2a)$$

where, a may be called the effective ionic diameter, and x , a dimensionless variable.

It follows from Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium that

$$f_o/f = n'/n \quad (2b)$$

where, n' represents the number of ions per unit volume inside the ion-atmosphere and n outside it. From equation (2) it follows that

$$(2n)^{1/3} = (2\pi a x)^{1/3} \quad (2c)$$

Now substituting $(1/2\pi a x)^{1/3}$ for $(2n)^{1/3}$ and n'/n for f_o/f in equation (1) and simplifying we get,

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTa} \right]^{1/2} \left[\frac{n'/n}{x} \right]^{1/2} [2n]^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

As n increases in equation (3), n'/n and also x diminish. Hence it is assumed that over a certain range of values of n the ratio $(n'n/x)$ remains constant. Therefore, for a certain value of n in the specified range, adjusting a and x in such a way that $x = (n'/n)$, we may express equation (3) as

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTa} \right]^{1/2} [2n]^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

Hence so long as a remains constant κ_m varies as $C^{1/3}$, i.e. as cube-root of concentration.

If there are n molecules of 1 : 1 electrolyte per cm^3 of the solution then the volume of a cell containing two oppositely charged ions is as

$$(1/n) = (L_o)^3 \quad (5)$$

and the average distance between the two ions if they behave as uncharged particles should be L_o .

It is to be noted that L of equation (2) is related to L_o of equation (5) as

$$L_o = (2)^{1/3} L = 2\pi a x (2)^{1/3} \quad (6)$$

It follows from equations (2) and (6) that L/x or L_o/x remains constant so long as a remains constant and they do not change with the dilution of the solution. In a cell containing two oppositely charged ions the actual distance between them will be much less than L_o owing to electrostatic attraction. Let it be $2\pi a$, where a has the dimension of length. The electrostatic attraction decreases the distance L_o to $2\pi a$ along the line joining the centers of the ion-pair, so that the pressure inside the cell of volume $[(L_o^3)/2\pi a]$ remains the same as it was in the cell of volume $(L_o)^3$ when the two ions behaved as uncharged particles. Therefore,

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TABLE 1—POTENTIAL ENERGY AND THRESHOLD FREQUENCY OF THE ION-PAIR

Electrolyte used	Observed $\frac{A}{\text{Å}}$	Corrected $\frac{a}{\text{Å}}$	Concn. (M) C	$-\frac{e^2}{D(2\pi a)} \times 10^{-12}$	Frequency $\times 10^{11}$
HCl	13.40	16.88	0.0006 – 0.00029	2.72	4.17
	5.59	7.04	0.001 – 0.1	6.54	9.99
KCl	10.10	12.73	0.001 and lower	3.60	5.50
	5.42	6.88	0.002 – 0.1	6.73	10.28
NaCl	10.10	12.60	0.001 and lower	3.65	5.57
	5.52	6.95	0.002 – 0.1	6.60	10.08
KNO ₃	10.40	13.10	0.009 and lower	3.51	5.33
	4.80	6.05	0.001 – 0.0037	7.61	11.60
	3.99	4.27	0.005 – 0.1	10.75	16.41
AgNO ₃	11.40	14.36	0.0005 and lower	3.19	4.87
	5.43	6.84	0.0007, 0.004	6.72	10.26
	3.20	4.03	0.005 – 0.1	11.40	17.40

n'/n should be equal to $(L_0)^3/L_0^3(2\pi a)$ or $(2)^{1/3}x$. Substituting this value of n'/n in equation (3) we get,

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTA} \right]^{1/3} [(2)^{1/3}]^{1/2} [2n]^{1/3} \quad (6a)$$

$$= \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTA} \right]^{1/2} [2n]^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

In equation (7), $A = a/(2)^{1/3}$ and it remains constant so long as a remains constant.

Application of quantum theory :

In the previous section we have used the concept of ion-pair consisting of two oppositely charged ions of an 1 : 1 electrolyte and the distance between their centres as $2\pi a$. Let us now assume^{7,8} that each ion-pair rotates about an axis perpendicular to the line joining their centres and passing through the centre of gravity of the system. According to equation (2), $L = 2\pi ax$, so it follows that

$$2\pi yL = 2\pi a(2\pi yx) \quad (8)$$

Putting $yx = w$ and treating it as frequency of rotation, it follows from equation (8) that $2\pi yL$ represents velocity, say, v . The centrifugal force is then equal to

$$[(Mf_1mf_2)/(Mf_1 + mf_2)][2\pi yx]^2(2\pi a)$$

where, M and m represent the masses in vacuum, of the positive and the negative ions of the ion-pair, and f_1 and f_2 are the corresponding correction factors† for the buoyancy effect of water.

The electrostatic attraction between the ions forming the ion-pair is equal to $e^2/(2\pi a)^2D$, where D is the dielectric constant of water and $2\pi a$ the distance between them. Since the system is in equilibrium the electrostatic attraction balances

†Let d_1 , d_2 and d_0 be the densities of the positive and negative ions and that of the solution, then $f_1 = (d_1 - d_0)/d_1$ and $f_2 = (d_2 - d_0)/d_2$.

the centrifugal force. Therefore,

$$\frac{e^2}{D(2\pi a)^2} = \left[\frac{Mf_1mf_2}{Mf_1 + mf_2} \right] (2\pi yx)^2(2\pi a) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{e^2}{D(2\pi a)} = \left[\frac{Mf_1mf_2}{Mf_1 + mf_2} \right] (2\pi yx)^2(2\pi a)^2 \quad (9a)$$

The kinetic energy of the same system is given by

$$\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{Mf_1mf_2}{Mf_1 + mf_2} \right] (2\pi yx)^2(2\pi a)^2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{D(2\pi a)} \quad (10)$$

The potential energy, i.e. the energy required to separate the two ions from the distance $(2\pi a)$ to infinity is

$$[-e^2/D(2\pi a)] \quad (11)$$

Since the total energy w of the system is equal to the sum of the potential and kinetic energies, so we may write,

$$w = \frac{-e^2}{D(2\pi a)} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{D(2\pi a)} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{D(2\pi a)} \quad (12)$$

It follows from equations (10) – (12) that so long as a remains constant the kinetic energy, the potential energy and the total energy of the ion-pairs do not vary with dilution. In a previous publication⁹ it has been found that A remains constant upto a certain level of concentration, then changes over a narrow zone of concentration and becomes constant again. This will be evident from the data recorded in Table 1.

Processing of the data in Table 1 : The equivalent conductivity data recorded in Table 1 have been collected from Shedlowski's paper⁹. Column 2 of Table 1 records the observed values of A and column 3 the corrected value $(2)^{1/3}A$ according to equation (6a). Column 4 records the molar concentration range in which A remains constant. Column 5 records the values of the potential energy calculated by using the equation, $-e^2/D(2\pi a)$.

Column 6 records the threshold frequency ν calculated by using the equation, $e^2/D(2\pi a) = h\nu$.

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data (Table 1) that in the cases of HCl, NaCl and KCl the value of a changes twice in the concentration range 0.00027–0.1 *M*. In the cases of the nitrates of K^+ and Ag^+ the value of a changes thrice in the same concentration range. In every case, a increases with the increase of dilution. If we denote the values of a and ν at the highest dilution by A_1 and ν_1 and that of the next dilution by A_2 and ν_2 , respectively, then for the chlorides of Na^+ and K^+ the ratios of A_1 to A_2 are 1.81 and 1.86 and for the nitrates of K^+ and Ag^+ the ratios are 2.17 and 2.10, respectively.

The ratio ν_2/ν_1 of the threshold frequencies also shows the similar variations. It follows from Bohr's theory⁷, a varies directly as n (quantum number) and inversely as momentum p . Attention

may also be drawn to the fact that in the expression for the potential energy, $-e^2/D(2\pi a)$, all the terms except a are universal constants and their values are accurately known. To get an accurate value of this energy, therefore, it is necessary to find the precise value of a in every case.

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